

USMAN H. DUKKU

CONSERVATION OF LOCAL HONEYBEE POPULATIONS:
THE AFRICAN PERSPECTIVE

Conservazione delle colonie locali di Apis mellifera: prospettive in Africa

This presentation, based mostly on the speaker's involvement in honeybee research in Nigeria and the neighbouring countries of Niger, Cameroon and Chad, highlights the current conservation status of the Western honeybee, *Apis mellifera*, in Africa. It also attempts to identify human activities, including beekeeping, that impact local honeybee populations. Traditional beekeeping is the dominant practice on the continent. It is characterized by the use of single-chambered fixed-comb hives made from cheap, locally-available and environmentally friendly materials such as reeds and clay. Such hives are often placed in trees, scattered over a wide area, to attract wild swarms. The tropical climate permits year-round availability of forage; leading to continuous reproductive swarming and several harvests in the year with the number and yield varying with local conditions (an average of 25 kg per hive is typical). To cope with unfavourable environmental factors, colonies readily abscond or migrate. Thus, the continuous movement of colonies between apiaries and the natural environment prevents the creation of the artificial barrier between managed and wild colonies created by modern beekeeping in other places like Europe. Consequently, managed honeybee colonies in Africa are nothing but a tiny portion of the large wild population consisting of over 300 million colonies. Honey-hunting, fragmentation of habitats, frequent droughts, deliberate introduction of other subspecies of *A. mellifera* from other continents by developmental agencies are the major threats to local honeybee populations and, by extension, sustainable beekeeping in Africa. It is concluded that beekeepers' reliance on wild colonies to populate their

hives and the absence of practices such as breeding, trade in queens, migratory beekeeping and control of swarming seem to be the major factors contributing to conservation of the diversity of *A. mellifera* in Africa.

Authors' Address — U. H. DUKKU, Department of Biological Sciences, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi, Nigeria; email: udukku@atbu.edu.ng (ORCID: 0000-0002-5578-7950).